

THE ROLE OF ABDU DARUN SHRINE IN PILGRIMAGE TOURISM IN SAMARKAND

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11217602>

Abstract. *The article discusses pilgrimage tourism and its role in economic development. Also, there will be talk about the works being carried out in the Samarkand region, in particular, in the Abdu Darun shrine, in terms of the development of pilgrimage tourism. Pilgrimage tourism is aimed at getting in close contact with other cultures, acquiring historical knowledge about the history of other regions, visiting holy shrines, holy places.*

Keywords: *pilgrimage tourism, civilization, culture, shrine, Khoja Abdi Darun, halal tourism, ziyorat hona.*

INTRODUCTION

It is not an exaggeration to claim that tourism is today one of the driving forces behind global growth. According to analysts, tourism has become the most profitable business of the twenty-first century. That is why tourism has been identified as one of the 17 major objectives of the United Nations' 2030 sustainable development program. There are more than 200 types of tourism in the world, among which pilgrimage tourism is one of the fastest growing and promising directions. Our country used to be limited to historical and cultural tourism, but in the last five years special attention has been paid to pilgrimage tourism along with safari (desert), ethnographic and gastronomic new directions. Pilgrimage tourism (also called religious tourism) is a trip to places important to Muslim culture. For example, to memorial complexes and shrines. Organizers of this type of tourism create comfortable conditions by providing accommodation in a hotel according to halal standards and providing halal food. 3.5 thousand tourist objects in the country are directly related to Islam. Most of them are located mainly in Bukhara, Samarkand and Tashkent. Because Uzbekistan has a high potential in this regard it is true that they are not able to use their full potential. Islam in our country, which is known as the cradle of civilization, the centre of enlightenment and culture, scholars, thinkers, and great saints who contributed to the development of our religion and world science have flourished. There is a great need in the world to visit their shrines and holy places. Tourism is crucial to Uzbekistan's economic development and prosperity, and in recent years, along with other fields of tourism, there has been a lot of focus on the development of pilgrimage tourism. Nowadays, there is a growing global interest in the study of worship and shrines, as holy sites are an important part of people's everyday lives. On February 24, 2021, Resolution No. 100 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures for the development of domestic and pilgrimage tourism" was adopted to provide scientifically based information about the objects. This decision established the Coordination Council for the Development of Pilgrimage Tourism.

Pilgrimage is a person's journey to various holy places to perform religious rituals. It refers to a person's pilgrimage to religious or secular holy places away from his permanent residence. The external form of pilgrimage serves as the basis of pilgrimage tourism. Because in the process of external pilgrimage, pilgrims travel to visit holy places. This form of pilgrimage helps people to reach their spiritual and physical maturity. Pilgrimage tourism has great social and traditional significance. Visiting holy places allows the person of industrial society to enter into a dialogue

with his spiritual experiences. Religious pilgrimage and, in turn, it is divided into religious beliefs typical of Islam, Buddhism, Christianity, and Hinduism. If religious pilgrimage means worshipping holy things and places, secular pilgrimage is expressed in visiting and appreciating natural and living things and holy places.

The potential of pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan is greater than its current use. It has the potential to promote Uzbekistan as a global centre of civilization, gain recognition from international organizations, diversify services, and boost tourism exports. And the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Uzbekistan To ensure the implementation of Decree No. PF-6165 of February 9, 2021, on measures to further develop domestic and pilgrimage tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan, on May 20, 2022, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan organized and organized the "Week of International Pilgrimage Tourism" transfer measures Resolution No. 282.

According to the latest data, there are about 1.9 billion Muslims in the world. In Uzbekistan, 75% of the population is Muslim. Currently, it is decided to increase the number of visits of pilgrims from Indonesia, Malaysia, India, Pakistan, Bangladesh and Arab countries, which have a high potential of pilgrimage tourism, to the historical cities of our country, in particular to Samarkand. According to Crescent Rating, a group specializing in Muslim tourism, the segment of Muslim tourists is currently growing. By 2026, the number of tourists who believe in Islam will reach 230 million. (online source available at <https://oz.sputniknews.uz/20220618/makka-uzoq-ozbekiston-yaqin-ziyosat-turizmi-qanday-rivojlanmoqda-25437457.html>).

Source: made by author according to statistics of the State Tourism Committee of Uzbekistan (2022-2023)

The given diagram shows indicators of the State Statistics Committee on the flow of tourists to Uzbekistan. Citizens of neighbouring countries do not need a visa to visit to Uzbekistan. Important: all of the above countries have a large Muslim population, which means that there is a potential audience for pilgrimage tourism.

Today, there are 98 potential cultural heritage sites in Samarkand region, 51 of which are currently included in tour routes. In Samarkand, every street, water body has its own history, and at the same time, there are still unexplored, unimproved, neglected destinations. For example, the Mausoleum of Khoja Abdi Darunee. The Mausoleum of Khoja Abdi Darunee in Samarkand was

one of Central Asia's most respected shrines. This religious-memorial ensemble at Samarkand's Old Cemetery revolves on the burial of Abd-al Mazeddin, a 9th century Arab jurist and judge. Abd-al Mazeddin, also known as Khoja Abdi, Abdi-Darun, or Abdu-Daru, was a Sharia law specialist who rose to become one of the city's most recognized kadis, or judges. The ensemble was rebuilt in the 15th century, and a single-room prayer and memorial room known as a ziyorat hona was created beside the tomb. A mosque with a winter prayer hall, a modest minaret, and an aivan (raised, covered platform) was built in the 19th century. The platform is ornamented with carved wooden columns with piled stalactite capitals and vibrant, multicolored shades painted between the beams and sits in front of a pond. Numerous renovations of the ensemble have greatly affected its look throughout the ages, and the original edifices have sadly not survived to this day. The existing mausoleum is a modest square construction on an octagonal foundation with a pyramidal roof. The mausoleum's inside is sparse, missing the ceramics and gilded accents that one would expect from such a prestigious tomb. Instead, the mausoleum's walls and dome are covered in white stucco, and a massive gravestone covers practically the whole inside mausoleum. Today, the complex, which is managed by the Samarkand regional branch of the Public Charitable Foundation "Vaqf", is being repaired. The mosque is being completely rebuilt. While the mausoleum is being renovated by the Vaqf Foundation, a large mosque based on national architectural standards is being built with the help of locals and generous people to accommodate 7,000 worshipers. Construction began in March 2019. Today, the walls of the 39x41 3-storey khanaqah and the tower are being erected. A 100-seat toilet has been built and completed. The final decoration is underway. Construction of service rooms, auxiliary rooms, exterior facades and beautification works are being carried out at the same time. The mosque will be the second largest mosque in the province in terms of capacity after the recently completed mosque in Urgut district. Imam of the mosque is Zafar Mahmudov.

CONCLUSION

Taking into account that there are opportunities for the development of almost all types of tourism in the regions, it is necessary to carry out the necessary work to increase the efficiency of their development. Among other shrines such as Shahi Zinda, Gurimir and Imam Al Bukhari which are situated in Samarkand region, Khoja Abdu Darun shrine has an incomparable place in the development of pilgrimage tourism. Those who come to visit holy places do not limit themselves to visiting the graves of saints, of course. They visit other noteworthy historical and cultural objects and architectural monuments of the cities. Lifestyle, traditions, customs, immortal values of the local population and get acquainted with modern life. They use city and intercity transport and means of communication. They eat national dishes and buy various souvenirs and national costumes. So, the economic and financial importance of pilgrimage tourism is also great. Pilgrimage tourism has great spiritual, political, and social benefits, as well as financial resources such as donations, and charities, which, if used appropriately, will cover the economic costs incurred. Moreover, all the expenses provided to the foreign pilgrim tourist for the above-mentioned services are not free. If this recommendation is implemented, the tourism infrastructure will develop, the scale of attracting investments to new projects will increase. This, in turn, determines measures to systematically organize and improve the quality of services to residents and tourists at tourism facilities. In recent years, pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan has become one of the general aspects of tourism, a number of measures are being implemented to develop it as a network, to strengthen its material and technical base, to form its infrastructure, to provide the industry with medium-specialized and highly qualified personnel.

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